

Women's Contribution to the Development of Trade Union Movement in Tamilnadu

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M.Shankara Pandiyan

Research Scholar

P.G. & Research Department of History, Queen Mary's College, Chennai

Abstract

This information gives an detailed account of women working to the growth and development of the Trade Union Movement. In Tamil Nadu we can see the how for trade union activity is being carried out. Here we can found participation of the women in large number. It is very sad to see here that women faces problems in working areas during British period also.

Introduction

Aanum Pennum Nigarenak Kolvathal
arivilongi ivvvaiyam thazhaikumaam

- Bharathi

These are the words which is being taken from the poetic lines from his Kavithaigal. He is also one who asked the Women to come out from their home. First World War (1914-1918) has not changed the political conditions of the world. However also it has a great impact on socio, cultural, economic conditions of Human beings. It is also helped the women to go and work on the factories. In Madras presidency, the regions like Madras, Madurai and Coimbatore played an active role in developing Tradeunion movement. Annie Beasant who came from outside the India, helped the workers to come out from their problems. After facing the problems from the British government, she tried her level best to win from their suppressive tactics. Her contributions to this can be seen through her writings and speeches, especially in the Newspaper like "New India" when Wadia and K.C. Desikachari had fought for new India deterlined on July 31. The note entitled 'No on side issues' reveals the attitude of the Home Rulers towards the place of labour in the movement, In the great struggle for Indian freedom we cannot spare and bravest soliders from the battle front concept our bravest soldiers from the battle front for the sake of that freedom. They must not be captured on side issues. The labour struggle is important as it is in this great campaign. Winning home rule ultimately would lead to the labour issues. Winning Home Rule ultimately lead the labour to win its freedom. Till it is won labour's champions, if Home Rulers will be stuck down under any convenient pretent. Every one clearly knows

that the Amritsar session of Indian National Congress 1919 was significant in the history of labour movement in India as it also created the objective that asked her in provincial committees and other affiliated organizations to promote labour unions throughout the country with the aim of improving the social, economic and political conditions of the laboring masses and securing for them a fair standard of living and a proper place in the body politic of India. But this resolution was not fully supported by her. In a signed editorial in the newspaper New India on January 20, 1920, she said that this the new form of exploitation of labour, it is one of the gaining of the Political ends for the non-labourers. In her point of view, she criticized the Politicians that they were more dangerous than the capitalist, for the capitalist at least gave the existing pittance whereas the politician gave nothing.

Middle class women's organization under the leadership of Mrs. Annie Beasant and Women's Indian Association of Madras (WIA) has conducted survey in the year 1926 found that there is a gap which is being prevailed between men and women workers in terms of kinds of works which is being assigned to them. WIA found that living conditions, as well as working conditions were worst. No arrangements were made for sanitary and rest rooms, and there is no room to feed their children. There came a number of factory Acts in following years such as 1891, 1908, 1922. First, regulations were made to limit the number of hours women could work in the factory and also made provisions for the rest hours for the women who could work in the factory. By the B.P. Wadia, There were 3,000 men and 20 women and it was announced that 100 more women had joined the union. In 1930 on 8th June public meeting at any rate, had only the employers and their employers wanted men workers to realize that unless they treated their women-folk well at home, they should not expect better treatment from their employers. He was clear that the trade union movement could not grow strong and healthy without women's active participation in union work. Although these unions were predominantly male in composition they also took up the demands of the women workers. The unions like Madras labour union, Coimbatore labour union, Madras labour union, Coimbatore socialist textile workers union took up women's issues like maternity benefit, rest hours, increased wages in general and provision of canteens. It is interesting to find that Madras Labour union on April 30, 1930 decided to give all its members maternity benefit. Choolai mill which comes under the same union demanded an increase in wages for women in the reeling department in the year 1929. They also demanded an increase in the wage of women waste pickers which had reduced by the management on account of shortage of work at the mill for them. Already women were facing so many responsibilities from their homes, by taking care for their children, properly maintaining, second further advocated the measures for the prevention of women from over exploitation from their factories and they suggested to limit the hours from 5 am – 7 pm. Third, Indian factory Act which reduced the hours of women to work into eleven and half of a rest time. Fourth, government further proceeded that to stop the women and children from the heavy and dangerous work and stop the women working in the night. In the history of labour in that draft convention was passed in International Labour Conference held in the year 1919 at Washington. After this incident took place in the year 1920, maternity benefit was introduced for the first time by the Basel Mission at Madras and it was passed in the year 1934 in Madras. The union such as Madras corporation union and PWD union asked for the implementation of maternity benefits scheme, facilities for the creches, milk for the children of women workers. Once the problems of minimum wages, implementation of maternity benefit were accepted on one side on other side, the end of the thirties cotton mills witnessed a series of strikes for better wages and good working conditions, in general in which women's participation were very high. The year 1918 is the first instance of women being participated in the union proceedings. According to the CID report which gives the information that on December 9, 1918. This was the Public meeting namely the Madras Labour Union at Perambour which is being addressed.

Their households facing problems from their management. Again she have to face the problems from their masters in factories of Madurai. The role of Mason is to employ the workers and act as a role of supervisor and recruiting agent. Workers were completely controlled by him and complaints against Mason were more in number. The Mason used four language and calling women immediatly if their productivity came below the expectations of the supervisors in the mill. Till now women have to face the problems of matanity benefit. Besides, wages, and they have to fight for their honour now, Madura mill stike took place in the year April 22 – June 1, 1920. The reason for starting of the stike was on the misbehavior of Gurusamy Naidu, the head masitri with a women vellayammal who was dismissed on flimly reason of wasting cotton. Women they demanded dismissal of Mason and they wanted replacement of female Mason on 12th April. This was the increasing desire of women workers to join the union and fight for the letter conditions of the working. When the women expressed their desire to organise themselves, the masitri began sytamatic bullying and abusing the women, making their working life miserable and unbearable. The strike was the first of its kind in annals of the Indian history according to the Hindu Newspaper. There was a strike in Madurai on March 29, 1938 by the union for distribution of paddy among the striking workers. The women who worked were not given the paddy. As a result of this they were keen on joining the work as soon as the mills were reopened. From this we can see that the gender differentiation was followed. Thus differential treatment probably has its roots in a perception which refused to see women as bread winners rather, they were despite their partipation in wage war, still primarily viewed as dependents on male.

Coimbatore is one of the important and industrial centre in Presidency of Madras. Here also we can see how for the labour problems have reached its peak. Women workers of stane mills agitated against these practices and called for a strike to put an end to all these evils. Strike continued for many days from October 1946, but no solution was found. On Novemer 1946 the men workers also joined them. No proper steps were taken by the government though the workers approached them so many times. In the meantime the management decided to run the mill with outsiders, who supported them. The mill workers decided to blockade the mill activities and protested. The black sheep who supported the mill owners they stamped on the workers who were sitting infront of the mill gate and entered into the mill. Infuriated men workers assulated the traitors. The polie forces which were watching came up front and charged the workers with their riffle butts. A wome employee name Ammu prevented the policemen, when they attacked her with riffle butts. The angry policemen pushed her down and stamped on her with boot and injured her grievously and in her neck and heart. She had an heavy blood loss. Womens were arrested by the police. Peace returned to Stanes Mills but also suffering did not get end. Govindammal, a women worked who works in the Rajalakshmi Mill was badly attacked. When she was working in the spinning section. She and her husband had participated in the union actitivites and fought for the rights of the workers when the management got infuriated she was beaten up heavily with spinning wheels. She fainted due to the videt action and they decided that she was dead. She was recoved finally and she was actively participated in the union activities. Later she became a notable leader of 'Madhar Sangha' (i.e. Women's club) once the women come out from their traditional and religious barriers only the Consciousness on trade unionism will grow. So far, only very few women have been trade union leaders, but when this number increases, membership will also undoubtedly increase. Women workers still need to be guided by women leaders in order to imbibe progressive ideas. The pioneer trade union women leaders have before them the great task not only of educating women workers to join trade unions, but also of keeping trade unionism free from all personal or political motives and to work purely for the welfare of the worker. With this, we can conclude by sayig women's role in the trade union movement in Tamilnadu were highly remarkable. Today at the present conditions women were there in all sectors, still many women suffer a lot.

Conclusion

Though Women had their placed in higher level in all the fields, she faced in all kinds of problems by the men. If working women faces this kind of problem the women from rural area finds very difficult to come out from their own problem government took seviere actions only like by the women in our country will solve otherwise it will keep on going.

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